

Towards an Empathetic and Meta-Cognitive Digital Therapy Framework

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Abstract. We present an early design of Mindful-AI, a digital therapy framework that perceives multimodal affect, plans Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) strategy and self-monitors its own language. The proposed model architecture consists of a state vector incorporating sentiment, Electroencephalogram (EEG) band-power, heart-rate variability (HRV) and galvanic skin response (GSR), a reinforcement learning (RL) planner that learns to probe, reflect or reframe, a large language model (LLM) that generates the chosen act in natural language and a critic either accepts, regenerates or escalates the reply. Preliminary results suggest the potential of the proposed therapy agent in real world settings.

1 Introduction

Globally, more than one billion people live with a mental disorder. However, the mental health services remain chronically understaffed [1]. Artificial intelligence (AI) driven digital mental health applications are emerging as an alternative solution. From early rule trees such as Eliza [2] to modern LLM applications such as Woebot [3], Wysa [4] and Koko [5] have reached tens of millions of users worldwide [6]. However, there are limitations in these digital therapy applications that are necessary to be addressed in order to scale up their use worldwide and increase their effectiveness. Lack of embodied empathy is one of the limitations. Primarily, this arises from the absence of physiological measures and the lack of adaptation to hidden affect. Another less explored aspect is metacognitive self-monitoring. This may lead to LLMs outputting fluent but clinically unsafe advice. Moreover, missing theory of mind is another limitation where static templates cannot reason over a user’s evolving beliefs.

We integrate a multimodal proximal policy optimisation (PPO) [7] planner, a finetuned Llama-3 model with CACTUS dataset [8], and a metacognitive filter. The agent senses sentiment, HRV and GSR, chooses a CBT strategy, verbalises it, then self-critiques before replying. Ongoing work shows the potential of real world applicability in digital mental health context with promising preliminary results.

2 Background

Pure text sentiment misses activation and stress markers. State of the art EEG affect work reports θ , α and β waves corresponding to stress [9]. HRV correlates with emotion regulation capacity [10], while GSR tracks sympathetic activation[11]. Combining these with linguistic cues yields a richer affective state space.

Metacognition considers monitoring and controlling of thoughts and behaviour[12]. In the context of digital therapy this can correspond to filtering inaccurate or unsafe therapeutic responses. Prior digital therapy work relies on static toxicity filters. Meanwhile, critic guided approaches [13, 14] show effectiveness in automatically flagging hallucinated or off-topic replies.

No prior digital therapy system unifies multimodal empathy, metacognitive self-repair and LLM fluency. Mindful-AI fills this gap.

3 Proposed Digital Therapy Framework

The proposed framework consists of four subsystems: Perception, Planner, Generator and Meta-cognition.

3.1 Multimodal Perception Pipeline

The initial perception pipeline considers a simulated environment where the user perception is generated synthetically. This can be translated to a wearable devices interface with no changes to the internal functionality. Each dialogue turn is encoded as a state vector s_t . Sentiment score $s \in [-1, 1]$ is calculated by a RoBERTa model [15] fine-tuned on GoEmotions dataset [16]. We consider relative band powers θ (4-8 Hz), α (8-13 Hz) and β (13-30 Hz), averaged over a 1 second window. HRV is represented by root mean square of successive differences (ms) averaged over the last 30 beats and GSR by tonic skin conductance (μS) median over last 10 seconds. These ranges mimic empirical sensor data and allow the simulator to be swapped for live feeds without retraining. Accordingly we define the state representation as:

$$s_t = \langle s, \theta, \alpha, \beta, \text{HRV}, \text{GSR} \rangle. \quad (1)$$

3.2 Deep Reinforcement Learning based Planner

Planner consists of a deep reinforcement learning based on PPO algorithm. Our reward aggregates three empirically validated markers described above: the difference in sentiment (Δs_t), HRV (ΔHRV_t) and GSR (ΔGSR_t). Accordingly, we formalise the per-turn reward as:

$$r_t = \Delta s_t + a \Delta \text{HRV}_t - b \Delta \text{GSR}_t, \quad a = 0.02, b = 1. \quad (2)$$

where the scaling parameters a and b are chosen based on clinical evidence [10, 11].

Policy network consists of a two-layer tanh multi layer perceptron (64-32) outputs a softmax over three CBT strategies representing the action space. Model hyperparameters include Adam optimiser, learning rate = 3×10^{-4} , clip = 0.2, $\gamma = 0.99$ and GAE = 0.95.

3.3 Generator LLM

Llama-3.1-8B is fine-tuned using GaLore [17] on 6.5k CACTUS dialogues labelled with CBT strategy. Hyper-parameters include rank = 32, learning rate = 1×10^{-5} , and batch size = 32.

3.4 Meta-cognitive Filter

The proposed meta-cognitive filtering mechanism consists of two key components: (1) Detoxify [18] rejecting outputs with toxicity; (2) Critic framework [14] to constraint on the clinical-risk. One re-generation is allowed; a second failure triggers a safe-harbour message and human therapist intervention.

4 Experiments

4.1 Baselines

For LLM fine-tuning, we consider the base Llama 3.1 8B model as our baseline.

As typically in RL comparisons, we employ a random policy agent as our baseline for RL simulation. This agent chooses a random CBT strategy at a given turn. The rest of the implementation is the same as the Mindful-AI agent.

4.2 Preliminary Results

Fine-tuned LLM has shown significant improvement based on multiple objective metrics compared to the Base model. Figure 1 presents the results. Table ?? compares two responses generated from the Base and Fine-tuned models for the same user prompt showcasing the more empathetic, human like nature of the finetuned model.

Fig. 1: Comparison of evaluation metrics across dialogue turns.

For evaluations of the planner module, both models are trained for 400 simulated dialogues and tested with 120 new seeds. Each policy runs for 200 turns. Figure 2 presents the preliminary results.

Fig. 2: Boxplots showing the comparative performance for simulation for Mindful-AI agent versus Random CBT strategy agent

5 Conclusion and Further Work

Mindful-AI unites multimodal empathy, RL planning and metacognitive self-repair. Preliminary simulation results suggest the effectiveness of the proposed approach compared to a non-perception based therapy agent. Future work will focus on inclusion of SUDS ratings (subjective units of distress) as an additional modality in the perception module, in-cooperating the topic of CBT session into the reward criteria, integrating live wearable data and conducting a validation study with human participants.

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